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Methodology for Embedding Cancer Germline Variants

Giovanni Visonà, Gabriele Schweikert, Bernhard Schölkopf

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1 Germline Variants in Cancer

Genetic variations between individuals come from two different mechanisms. *Germline Variants* are inherited from our parents. In contrast, *Somatic Mutations* are acquired during the lifetime of an individual due to errors in the DNA replication mechanism, exposure to external factors, and imperfect repair processes. An average human genome presents a few million sequence variants compared to the reference genome [5]. Germline variants are part of an individual's genetic makeup and are shared between all cells, while somatic mutations are present only in a portion of them.

Both these mechanisms play a crucial role in complex disorders, especially in cancer [8]. However, common genetic variants explain only a small portion of the genetic burden in carcinogenesis [3]. While some known inherited mutations carry considerable risks, such as mutations in the *TP53* gene that lead to a 90% lifetime risk of developing cancer for mutation carriers [13], the role of inherited variants in the development of cancer is not yet wholly understood [15]. One of the most commonly accepted models of the impact of germline variants on cancer is Knudson's two-hit hypothesis [14]. In this model, one allele of a tumour-suppressor gene is affected by a germline variant. A somatic mutation can cause Loss of Heterozygosity (LOH) and disrupt the second allele, thus initiating the oncogenesis process.

An incredibly challenging hurdle in our understanding of cancer is that the vast majority of mutations occur in non-coding portions of the genome, and a non-trivial number of such mutations are *driver* mutations [16, 12, 7]. Mutations

in the exome often cause structural changes to the protein produced in the genes. In contrast, non-coding driver mutations affect the expression levels of the genes they regulate by affecting *cis*- and *trans*- regulatory regions. The best-characterised case of such non-coding driver mutations is the variation in the *TERT* promoter region, associated with melanoma, glioma, and other cancers [10, 22, 9].

A vast majority of the literature focuses on the study of somatic mutations. Clinical analysis of the impact of germline variants is crucial for improving our understanding of cancer. However, experimental conditions, software pipelines, and analysis methods present non-trivial challenges and often lead to conflicting claims [2].

Recently, a landmark study [11] produced the most extensive analysis of pathogenic germline variants in cancer to date, discovering 853 pathogenic or likely pathogenic variants in $\sim 8\%$ of the 10,389 cancer samples analysed. This work constitutes a significant step in developing a proper understanding of germline variants.

This proposal provides a methodology to embed germline variant profiles by combining domain knowledge and unsupervised representation learning. The learned representation can be used for a diverse set of downstream tasks to improve our understanding of the genetic burden of germline mutations in cancer.

2 Data

Variant calling, i.e. the procedure of identifying genetic variants, requires the use of specialised software tools such as HaplotypeCaller [4]. The natural variation in the human genome requires large amounts of data to overcome the low-signal to noise ratio for pathogenic variants and gain meaningful insights into their role in cancer. It has recently become possible to overcome this challenge due to large-scale projects like The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA).

The recent work of Huang et al. [11] has produced a dataset of germline variants in cancer samples from a TCGA cohort, with stringent quality control criteria. This dataset, available through the Genomic Data Commons (GDC)¹, includes germline variants in 10,389 samples from 33 cancer types. A tiny subset of the 286,657,499 exonic variants have been classified as Pathogenic, Likely Pathogenic, and Prioritised Variants of Unknown Significance (VUSs).

To the best of our knowledge, this dataset represents the most extensive collection of cancer germline variants. As such, we propose it as a suitable candidate for the implementation of the embedding methodology.

3 Model

Machine learning models applied to somatic mutations often encode these mutations at the gene level (e.g. [18]). This approach limits the domain of appli-

¹<https://gdc.cancer.gov/about-data/publications/PanCanAtlas-Germline-AWG>

cation to mutations in the exome. However, since the selected dataset of cancer germline variants contains only exonic variants, this offers a suitable approach that enables the use of unsupervised representation learning models.

We can implement this approach by encoding each of the 10,389 samples in the dataset as a vector. Each component of this vector corresponds to a gene and can be assigned a binary value to indicate whether any mutation is present in that specific gene in the sample considered.

The model that we propose follows this procedure but introduces two additional features that offer exciting opportunities to improve the overall performance:

- We do not encode the mutation data as a vector, but we overlay it on a suitable *molecular network* (e.g. a Protein-Protein Interaction network from STRING db² [20]). The inclusion of the graph structure introduces in the model domain knowledge and an inductive bias that represents the interaction between the components. To overlay the information, we can encode the network as an undirected graph and assign binary values to the nodes representing the presence of mutations.
- We apply a *message passing/network propagation* [6] algorithm to the resulting molecular network for a fixed number of steps. The propagation process produces a set of networks, one per iteration, each capturing a different locality level in the data, akin to sequential convolution operations. With this feature, germline profiles that affect the same sub-networks of the molecular network can share a portion of the features since mutations in adjacent nodes produce a similar pattern after propagation. A simple vectorial representation would not include this information.

The set of networks resulting from these two modifications can be encoded either in an unsupervised manner, with methodologies such as graph2vec [17] and InfoGraph [19], or in a supervised fashion, using Graph Neural Networks [23] and the cancer type as the label. The embeddings from each propagation step are then concatenated to produce a learned representation for the germline variant profile of a single sample (Figure 1).

The main advantage introduced by the proposed model is the inclusion of relevant domain knowledge as inductive bias. Molecular networks capture relationships between genes that a vectorial representation would otherwise ignore. The choice of one or multiple biological networks can also include different layers of information. Additionally, the propagation steps capture different levels of locality that allow mutation profiles to share a portion of the features if they affect the same subnetworks of the molecular network.

One of the main downsides of such a method is that it only allows the embedding of exonic variants, which is not a comprehensive representation of the naturally occurring germline variants, as previously described.

²<https://string-db.org/>

Figure 1: Illustration of the graph propagation embedding scheme. We encode the variant profile as an undirected graph whose nodes have binary values representing the presence of mutations. A network propagation algorithm produces a set of graphs that capture the network’s connectivity at different locality levels. The network resulting from each step is embedded using an unsupervised algorithm such as InfoGraph. The resulting set of representations is concatenated to obtain a representation for the variants profile.

4 Evaluation and Baselines

The evaluation of the learned embeddings involves the use of such representations for suitable downstream tasks.

A typical evaluation task in this type of study is the classification of the cancer type (e.g. [18]). While simple in implementation, this task is of limited interest for clinical applications, as there is no practical need for a machine-learning algorithm to determine the origin site of cancer.

Recent advances in cancer study revealed deeper connections across cancer

types, related to mutational signatures and driver mutations [21, 1]. These biomarkers offer exciting opportunities for diagnostic and therapeutic developments. Therefore, a more exciting task involves finding connections between cancers regardless of the origin site. The dataset considered describes 853 pathogenic or likely pathogenic variants. A possible measure of evaluation for the quality of the learned representations is the cluster co-occurrence of pathogenic variants.

As comparison baselines, the performance of the learned embedding can be compared to the raw vectorial encoding of the mutations, to embeddings learned with a VAE model (Figure 2), and to the graph embeddings without propagation steps.

Figure 2: Baseline VAE model for the embedding of germline variants profiles.

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